

References

1. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 153.
2. J. SELBIN, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 293.
3. S. K. KSHER, S. K. SAHINI, V. KUMARI and R. N. KAPOOR, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, 37, 121.
4. A. JEZERSKI and J. B. RAYNOR, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 44, 153.
5. W. I. AZEEZ and A. F. KAZEER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, 36, 205.
6. G. C. SAXENA, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra University, 1976.
7. A. SYAMAL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 16, 309.
8. J. SELBIN and T. R. ORTOLANO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1253.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1971.
10. J. T. BELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, 31, 703.
11. J. A. DAY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1363.
12. D. M. ADAM, "Metal Ligand and Related Vibrations", Arnold, London, 1967.
13. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 3781.

Metal Derivatives of Antimony Thiocarboxylates. Part-IV. Complexes of Silver(I), Aluminium(III), Chromium(III), Iron(III), O-Zirconium(IV) and Thorium(IV) with Antimony Hydrogen Bis(thiolactate)

SNEH LATA, HEMANT K. SHARMA, S. N. DUBEY
and
D. M. PURI*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 26 April 1983, revised 2 May 1984,
accepted 20 September 1984

IN continuation to our studies on metal derivatives of antimony hydrogen bis-(thioglycollate) and -(thiolactate)^{1,2} we report here the syntheses and structural studies of the complexes of antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) with Ag^I, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, OZr^{IV} and Th^{IV}. Formation constant studies of Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes in aqueous medium have also been made.

Experimental

Materials: All the chemicals used were chemically pure. The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was prepared and purified by known methods^{3,4}.

Aluminium(III), chromium(III) and iron(III) sulphates (Merck, Pure), Ag^I, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} nitrates (B.D.H., Pure) solutions were used after analysis.

Preparation of complexes: To a solution of the ligand antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) in hot water, the required amount of aqueous metal ion solution was added depending upon the ratio in which the reaction was to be carried out. An

immediate precipitation of the complex occurred except for aluminium and chromium. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for some time for complete precipitation. The solid product was then filtered, washed with hot water and hot ethanol, and dried under reduced pressure (2 mm) at 50°.

In case of aluminium and chromium complexes, the precipitation was carried out by adding NaOH solution (0.1 N). Metals in the compounds were estimated by the known methods and the results are given in Table 1 along with other data.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.		
		Metal	C	H
Ag(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb)	White	23.86 (24.65)	15.82 (16.45)	1.78 (1.83)
Al(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	White	2.31 (2.65)	20.04 (21.25)	2.24 (2.36)
Cr(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	Bluish green	4.62 (5.00)	20.12 (20.74)	2.18 (2.30)
Fe(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	Dark brown	5.02 (5.34)	20.21 (20.66)	2.38 (2.30)
OZr(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	White	11.42 (11.90)	18.41 (18.78)	2.01 (2.09)
Th(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₄	White	14.10 (14.96)	17.93 (18.57)	1.94 (2.06)

Physical measurements: Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on Gouy balance. The diffused reflectance spectra were recorded on SP700 spectrophotometer. pH was measured with a Philips PR 9405M pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The instrument was calibrated using buffer tablets of pH 4 and 9.2.

Results and Discussion

The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was prepared as reported earlier³⁻⁵.

In the ir spectrum of thioacetic acid the carbonyl stretching vibrations (ν_{as} and ν_s) were observed at 1715 and 1680 cm⁻¹. These bands shifted to 1625 and 1450 cm⁻¹, respectively on the formation of organoantimony compounds, which further shifted to lower frequency in the ranges of 1570-1550 and 1400-1370 cm⁻¹ on complex formation with different metals as observed in their ir spectra. These lowerings suggest that COO⁻ acted as a bidentate bridging chelating ligand⁶ and is consistent with the results obtained in case of CaCu(OAc)₄·6H₂O⁷. The zirconium complex showed a sharp band at 870 cm⁻¹ (Zr—O)⁸.

Magnetic moments of Cr^{III} complex (4.14 B.M.) was consistent with the octahedral structure having d³ system¹, whereas electronic spectrum of Cr^{III} complex showed bands at 700, 490 and 380 nm as expected for octahedral coordination⁹.

The trivalent iron complex was found to have magnetic moment of 3.68 B.M., a value less than that

required for d^5 system, suggesting spin-spin coupling between unpaired electrons of neighbouring iron atoms^{10,11}. The bands at 700, 590 and 350 nm observed in the electronic spectrum of Fe^{III} complex could be attributed¹² to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(4G) \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4T_{2g}(4G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(4D) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$

Other complexes were found to be diamagnetic as was expected.

Thus, analytical data, high m.p., insolubility in different organic solvents and water, magnetic moment values, ir and electronic spectral data suggest these complexes to be polymeric in nature.

Formation constants of Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes: The dissociation constant of the ligand antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was determined by the differential method¹³ and the value was found to be 3.162×10^{-6} .

Metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting the values \bar{n} vs pL and stepwise formation constants, $\log K_n$, were determined using the following techniques^{14,15}, (i) interpolation of half \bar{n} values, (ii) pointwise calculation method, and (iii) curve-fitting method.

The final values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ for Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes were found to be 3.79, 3.23, 2.86, and 4.05, 3.52, 2.84, respectively.

The formation constants of the other metal ion complexes could not be determined due to immediate precipitation of the complex on titration.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully thank Prof. V. Yatirajam, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University for providing facilities. Two of the authors (S.L. and H.K.S.) are also thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial help.

References

1. H. K. SHARMA, SNEH LATA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 1031.
2. SNEH LATA, H. K. SHARMA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in the press.
3. P. KLASON and T. CARLSON, *Chem. Ber.*, 1906, 39, 732.
4. L. RAMBERG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1356.
5. HOLMBERG, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 56, 385.
6. C. A. MCAUTIFFE, J. V. QUAGLIANO and L. M. VALLARINO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1906.
7. D. A. LANGE and C. R. HARE, *Chem. Comm.*, 1967, 890.
8. L. N. KOMMISSAROVA, Z. N. PROZOROVSKAYA and V. I. SPITSYN, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1966, 11, 1089.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 308.
10. M. A. ALI, S. E. LIVINGSTON and D. PHILIPS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 5, 119; 1972, 6, 11, 39.
11. M. T. BECK, "Chemistry of Complex Equilibria", Van Nostrand Reinhold, London, 1970.
12. S. K. SENGUPTA, S. K. SAHNI and R. N. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 703.
13. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S. and Longmans Green, London, 3rd. ed., 1961, 931.
14. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
15. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 327.

Preparation and Characterisation of Mixed (Ca+Ba+Cu) Hydroxylapatites

PREMA N. PATEL*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Applied Chemistry,
G. M. College, Sambalpur-768 004
and

O. P. AGRAWAL

Department of Chemistry, Panchayat College,
Bargarh, Sambalpur

Manuscript received 16 June 1982, revised 5 March 1984,
accepted 20 September 1984

HYDROXYLAPATITE is assigned the formula $Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2(CaHA)$. In recent years, attention has been directed towards all of the basic calcium phosphates for the elucidation of the processes of calcification in general and for dentistry in particular. Hydroxylapatite is now recognised as the most important of the inorganic constituents of human bone and teeth^{1,2}. It belongs to an isomorphous series of compounds known as apatites. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions³. $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Ba^{2+}$ and/or Cu^{2+} replacement reactions in CaHA is of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} ions into human skeletal system according to the following equation.

Solid solutions of calcium, barium and copper hydroxylapatites were prepared earlier⁴ by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium, barium and copper hydroxylapatites at about 1300°. These samples prepared by the solid state reaction were, however, found to be discontinuous and non-homogenous.

Now an attempt has been made at a new method of preparation of the homogenous solid solutions of mixed (Ca+Ba+Cu) hydroxylapatites over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation⁵⁻⁸.

Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (Solution B) were prepared separately in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. The pH of the solutions were maintained at ~ 11 . A part of the Solution B was taken in a flask (2l) fitted with two separating funnels and a delivery tube. Solution A and Solution B taken separately in the separating funnels were then added dropwise simultaneously. Precipitation was carried out in CO_2 -free atmosphere and the medium was well stirred by bubbling CO_2 -free air.